

Developing a Pilot Data Trust for Open Access eBook Usage

Short summary of Technical Work Jan 2020 to March 2022

Goals

The goals of the technical work within the OAeBU project were to:

1. Engineer a data ingest system capable of bringing OA book usage data together from multiple publishers and platforms, and to integrate this via high quality bibliographic information
2. Build demonstration dashboards for a set of partners to explore the needs, use cases and potential value created by specific analytics solutions
3. Investigate and demonstrate the feasibility of creating benchmarks that enable the comparison of data from different publishers

Outcomes

Data Ingest and Workflow Systems

The project has delivered an open source set of workflows leveraging adjacent work by the Curtin team and existing technologies to build a highly scalable, secure and flexible set of open-source workflows that collect and integrate usage data from both proprietary/private and public data sources with future options for enrichment and expansion.

The technology stack uses the book-industry standard metadata interchange standard ONIX, combined with open bibliographic metadata to integrate usage data from multiple sources. Data integration through the OAeBU Workflows code base is built on an open source workflow system written in Python and built on AirFlow which ingests and combines data into a cloud database (Google BigQuery) which uses standard SQL for data operations. The OAeBU workflows disambiguate and combine data from multiple sources (e.g. OAPEN, COUNTER, JStor, Google Books) which may use differing identifier systems.

Data is pushed from the cloud datastore into Elasticsearch where it is accessible to Kibana, providing an open source data analytics and dashboarding system. Dashboards in Kibana are developed through a visual interface in collaboration with users, and are specified in JSON so they can be maintained and versioned in a code repository. Data access limitations flow through from the underlying sources into the cloud database and Elastic/Kibana where stakeholder data is sandboxed into separate areas with no cross access, providing strong security and privacy.

The entire stack from workflow system, through data ingest, database queries, data movement, and dashboard specification is maintained as an open source codebase under

an MIT License (<https://github.com/The-Academic-Observatory/oaebu-workflows>) and documented through the industry standard ReadtheDocs (<https://oaebu-workflows.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>).

To our knowledge this system is the only large-scale data integration system that provides scalable, open-source technology that is designed specifically for books and focuses on book industry standards such as ONIX. It is built on high-quality underlying technologies and standards (i.e. UTF-8 compliant technologies including SQL, Airflow, Python, ElasticSearch etc) that are capable of supporting multiple languages, including non-Latin scripts such as Chinese characters. Because the system focuses on provision of metadata from publishers, and using standards built for books, it is not limited by indexing or other visibility issues that are often problematic for scholarly books.

Dashboards

Dashboards have been built for partners on a range of platforms with the open-source Kibana platform being the main focus. Several rounds of partner engagement have helped to design a set of dashboards that are specific to each partner but also have a common design framework behind them. Through this work a number of data issues have been identified for future work and improvement. University of Michigan Press elected to make their dashboards publicly available.

At least one dashboard was created for each of the six project partners: ANU Press (ANU), University of Michigan Press (UoMP), UCL Press (UCL), Springer Nature, Wits University Press, and the OAPEN repository (OAPEN).

Preliminary Benchmarking

The capacity to build benchmarks was demonstrated by creating preliminary comparison points such as monthly downloads, downloads per country, and downloads per institution across publishers. This data was not added to dashboards because the scope of the current partners meant that these demonstration benchmarks were not appropriate for live decision making. Nonetheless the technical capacity to create benchmarks is in place, awaiting sufficiently broad data holdings and community discussion of the principles, ethics and uses of this type of analysis.

What We Learned

Collaboration with the diverse Dashboard Partners involved in this project made it possible to gain deep insight into the needs of different types of publisher in relation to the display of usage data. Important differences between partners were noted. This information will be used to refine the development of dashboard tools and services during the next project phases.

For example, some partners preferred to include a dashboard focused on author-level aggregation, while others did not. Partners also had differences in the presentation of their ONIX feed, with one ISBN per book title preferred by some partners, while others utilised a

workflow that aggregated related ISBNs (book products) into book works and book families. There were also partner specific preferences in the fields used to display downloads and views, with google books as an example (downloads represented by sales for some partners, versus book views with pages viewed by others).

The capacity of some partners to provide an ONIX feed and some platform data in the specifications required for our pipeline was also identified as a challenge for some of the smaller publishers, with implications for how a dashboarding service that supports smaller publishers may need to be designed in the future.

A specific issue that requires further work relates to the public/private nature of dashboards. The Kibana framework has solid security systems in place which make it challenging to make these dashboards fully public on the web. University of Michigan Press was keen to make their dashboard fully public and a system for managing this was developed. However in the longer term the balance between security, running costs and public facing dashboards will require further investigation.

Partners have indicated an interest in retaining these dashboards and engaging with the follow-on dashboard project. There is significant interest from other potential partners in having access to dashboard capabilities. Scaling and stabilising this platform will be the focus of a follow-on project, led by Lucy Montgomery at Curtin University, in collaboration with OAPEN and Educopia.